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Cite this article: Jeddi Y, Segovia-Martin J, Servan-Schreiber E. 2026 Crowdsourced versus large language models forecasting: evidence for the accuracy–correlation effect. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* **381**: 20240456.

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2024.0456>

Received: 30 May 2025

Accepted: 25 February 2026

One contribution of 17 to a theme issue ‘The evolution of collective intelligence’.

Subject Areas:

cognition, behaviour

Keywords:

large language models, forecasting, collective intelligence, hybrid groups

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Electronic supplementary material is available online at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.8404289>.

Crowdsourced versus large language models forecasting: evidence for the accuracy–correlation effect

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Over the past quarter century, crowdsourced forecasting has largely outperformed individual forecasters. Today, large language models (LLMs), aggregating human knowledge at scale, constitute a new form of collective intelligence (CI). A central question is how LLM predictive accuracy associates with human–AI correlation, and whether this relationship exceeds what would be expected if both merely track the same underlying truth. We investigate this through the accuracy–correlation effect (ACE), which posits that as algorithmic systems improve, they increasingly correlate with human predictions, potentially diminishing human value in hybrid ensembles. Using 76 model × prompt forecast sets from 16 LLMs on 580 resolved ForecastBench questions, we computed LLM accuracy and correlations with two human aggregates (superforecasters, general public), separately for databases ($n = 526$) and prediction markets ($n = 54$) questions. Linear mixed-effects models show a robust positive association between LLM accuracy and human–AI correlation that substantially exceeds independent-errors predictions. Correlations were lower for superforecasters than for the general public, and weaker for markets than for data questions. These results support ACE while indicating that increasing correlation reflects more than improved signal tracking alone, suggesting that simultaneous increases in accuracy and correlation may reduce optimal human weights in data-rich settings, while human judgement retains critical value in contextual reasoning scenarios.

This article is part of the theme issue ‘The evolution of collective intelligence’.

1. Introduction

Prediction is fundamental to human cognition and adaptation [1–3]. Our ability to anticipate future events, from immediate threats to long-term changes, has been vital to both individual survival and collective advancement [4]. Our predictive capability, refined over time, now extends beyond immediate survival to include complex societal needs: organizations forecast market trends, governments project economic indicators and scientists model climate patterns [5,6]. The last century has witnessed a transformation in predictive capabilities, driven by the convergence of statistical innovations [7,8], advances in machine learning algorithms and computer architecture [9–11] and exponential growth in processing power [12,13]. Yet despite these developments, accurate prediction remains one of the most challenging aspects of decision making [14–16], particularly when facing complex, dynamic systems with multiple interacting variables [17–19].

One reliable approach to addressing complex predictions has emerged through harnessing collective human judgement in what is known as

'crowdsourced forecasting'. Crowdsourced forecasting relies on human expertise, leveraging what Surowiecki termed the 'wisdom of crowds' [20]. This approach aggregates competitive predictions from diverse individuals through prediction markets or prediction polls [21] to produce forecasts often more accurate than those of individual experts [22–24]. Competitive forecasting tournaments [25] and prediction markets [26] have demonstrated how structured aggregation of human predictions can achieve remarkable accuracy across many domains. These tournaments not only validate the power of collective intelligence (CI), defined as groups of individuals acting together in ways that seem intelligent [27], but also provide frameworks for understanding why some forecasters consistently outperform others [28,29].

In parallel, artificial intelligence (AI) has evolved from rigid, rule-based systems to sophisticated learning algorithms capable of detecting complex patterns in data [30]. AI evolution has culminated recently in large language models (LLMs) that, in an interesting parallel to crowd wisdom, derive their capabilities from aggregating and synthesizing vast amounts of human-generated knowledge [31,32]. Just as crowdsourced forecasting leverages the diversity of human judgement [33], these models learn from the collective documentation of human experience and knowledge captured in natural language [31]. Through training on vast corpora of text, LLMs may have developed sophisticated capabilities in understanding context, drawing connections across domains and engaging with complex ideas, in some cases mirroring aspects of human cognition [34–36]. However, forecasting presents unique challenges that test the limits of artificial reasoning. Unlike many cognitive tasks where LLMs can learn from examples with known outcomes, forecasting requires reasoning about events that cannot be present in any training data. This fundamental constraint has important implications for how LLM systems perform in prediction tasks. Recent work shows that a single frontier LLM still trails the median human-crowd forecast [37], yet when integrated into retrieval-augmented pipelines or LLM ensembles, these artificial systems are competitive with human aggregates [38,39]. This has sparked growing interest in combining human and algorithmic predictions into hybrid forecasting systems, a promising direction for advancing predictive accuracy [40–43].

This evolving landscape raises our central research question: will humans continue to be of value in an era when LLMs can 'independently' process and synthesize massive amounts of information and generate forecasts that approach human crowd benchmarks? While LLMs offer unprecedented scalability and speed in analysing unstructured data [44,45], the human dimension encompassing contextual knowledge, creativity, moral reasoning and experiential insight, may still prove useful, particularly for ethical and complex scenarios [46–48]. Alternatively, as AI advances, it may progressively overtake functions previously thought to require human judgement [36,49–51], though the extent of this shift may vary across forecasting contexts.

To address the question above, we employ the theoretical framework developed by Hong *et al.* [41], which posits an 'accuracy–correlation effect' (ACE). ACE suggests two developments as algorithmic systems improve: they become more accurate and (if the features they use increasingly overlap with the information used by humans) their judgements become more correlated with human predictions. The latter phenomenon stems from the progressive convergence between the extensive, granular datasets or 'big data' [52] processed by algorithms and the contextually rich 'thick data' [53,54] utilized by human forecasters. While more limited in volume, thick data encompasses qualitative nuances and experiential knowledge that have traditionally been the domain of human judgement [55–57]. This convergence can occur through two mechanisms: algorithms may increasingly capture the underlying signals that humans track, and they may develop error patterns that increasingly resemble human biases and heuristics. Recent work has documented substantial correlated errors across LLMs, even among independently trained systems [58], yet far less is known about how such correlations manifest between LLMs and human forecasters, where correlation may reflect either shared information or shared biases. Understanding this distinction is necessary both to understand the current limits of ecosystem diversity and to more effectively engineer multi-agent forecasting systems [59].

Hong and colleagues argue that this convergence would, under ACE, reduce the value of human input in hybrid forecasting systems, though humans may retain advantages in certain scenarios. This occurs because the diversity benefit of incorporating multiple information sources diminishes as those sources become more similar [60,61]. Similarly, when machines process information in ways that increasingly overlap with human judgement, the novel perspective that humans once uniquely contributed becomes partially redundant. Within the context of crowdsourced forecasting, we address two research questions: first, to what extent does increasing LLM predictive accuracy associate with greater correlation to human crowd forecasts, and does this relationship vary systematically across forecasting contexts (question source, human forecaster group, prompting configuration)? Second, is any observed accuracy–correlation relationship driven by shared error patterns between humans and LLMs, or does it simply reflect both becoming more accurate at tracking the truth? We investigate whether patterns consistent with ACE manifest in LLM forecasting by examining whether models with higher forecasting accuracy demonstrate stronger correlation with human predictions. We additionally explore the mechanisms underlying human–AI correlation by decomposing correlation into components associated with overall accuracy versus shared residual errors. If empirical patterns align with Hong *et al.*'s theoretical framework, it would suggest that simultaneous increases in accuracy and correlation may influence optimal weights for human contributions in hybrid-ensemble systems, though our observational design precludes causal inference.

We analyse data from the ForecastBench LLMs benchmark [62], which provides forecasts from 16 LLMs across five major AI laboratories (OpenAI, Anthropic, Google, Mistral AI and Meta) and human forecasters (expert forecasters, including superforecasters, and lay forecasters recruited from Prolific) on 580 identical resolved questions, enabling direct comparison of accuracy and correlation patterns. We use ForecastBench's source-based categorization of market questions ($n = 54$) versus data questions ($n = 526$) as a coarse empirical proxy for examining whether ACE manifests differently across forecasting contexts. We employ mixed-effects modelling to assess whether patterns consistent with ACE manifest in LLM forecasting and compare observed relationships against an independent-errors null model to determine whether correlation exceeds what would be expected from humans and LLMs merely tracking the same underlying truth. In this study, we begin by reviewing the key empirical and theoretical underpinnings of both crowdsourced forecasting and LLM-based forecasting. We then present our empirical analysis and discuss the implications of observed patterns for human contributions in hybrid forecasting systems.

By examining this evolving relationship between human and artificial judgement in the domain of forecasting, our research contributes to both theoretical understanding of CI and practical applications in decision support systems. The findings could have implications not only for the design of future forecasting platforms but also for broader questions about the complementarity between human and machine intelligence in complex cognitive tasks.

2. Relevant literature

(a) Crowdsourced forecasting

Crowdsourced forecasting or crowd-forecasting refers to the systematic elicitation and aggregation of human probability assessments about future events [19,26,63]. It has emerged as a robust methodology for decision making under uncertainty. Unlike statistical forecasting that relies on historical data patterns [64,65], this approach incorporates human reasoning where past patterns may not reliably predict future outcomes. Individual forecasters draw on rich, contextual knowledge that may not be readily quantifiable to make forecasts. The individual probability judgements are aggregated (through betting in prediction markets or algorithms in prediction polls) into a collective forecast that is most often more accurate than the vast majority of individual forecasts. This result has been documented in domains as diverse as sports [66], box office [67], elections [68], geopolitics [19], public health [23], science [69], technology [70] and business [71].

Building on Galton's classic ox-weight demonstration [72] and popularized by Surowiecki [20], a wide literature shows that when forecasters are diverse [33], form their judgements independently [73] and their opinions are sensibly aggregated [21], the collective estimate often outperforms individual experts. Diversity supplies more unique information, independence curbs correlated bias and aggregation merges the signals into a more reliable consensus.

The Intelligence Advanced Research Projects Activity's tournaments, particularly the Good Judgment Project (GJP), advanced understanding of forecasting accuracy by identifying 'superforecasters' who consistently achieve exceptional prediction accuracy across diverse domains [19,29]. Effective aggregation mechanisms are central to crowd-forecasting systems, including price mechanisms used in prediction markets [26,74] and statistical algorithms like extremization, recency-weighted aggregation and performance-weighted combinations [21,22,75–77]. At the individual level, forecasting skill can be significantly improved through structured training in probabilistic reasoning and cognitive debiasing, early identification of skilled forecasters for targeted development, and effective team strategies that maintain individual accountability [28,29,78–80]. However, social influence and shared information environments can undermine aggregation benefits by reducing cognitive diversity [73,81].

The practical significance extends across critical domains. In geopolitical forecasting, GJP demonstrated that crowd-forecasting could outperform traditional intelligence analysis [29,82]. Financial platforms like Estimote use crowdsourced earnings forecasts for improved market efficiency [83]. During public health crises, crowd-based systems have proven valuable for predicting the severity of disease outbreaks [23,84].

(b) From crowds to silicon crowds: large language models in forecasting

Recent advances in LLMs have prompted exploration of their integration into forecasting contexts. LLMs derive predictive capacity from training on vast corpora including forecasting discussions, expert analyses and historical patterns, enabling them to generate context-sensitive predictions across multiple domains [37–39,85–87]. This training enables LLMs to process 'big data', which represents extensive, quantifiable information that can be algorithmically processed. Nevertheless, controlled evaluations show that an individual frontier model still trails the median human crowd and is prone to miscalibration, hallucinated evidence and data-cut-off blindness [38–40,85,88,89].

Retrieval-augmented pipelines [38,89–91] narrow that gap by letting an LLM autonomously search news feeds, summarize evidence, sample multiple forecasts, then ensemble the samples. Halawi and colleagues observed such systems approach crowd accuracy [38], especially early in a question's lifetime or when the crowd is more uncertain. Additionally, they noted that combining system predictions with crowd forecasts through weighted averaging improved overall accuracy, suggesting LLMs may be most valuable as complements rather than replacements for human judgement. Other researchers pursued a complementary route: aggregating 12 heterogeneous LLMs ('silicon crowds') [39]. Model diversity in architecture, training data and prompting style boosted accuracy to a level statistically indistinguishable from human aggregates. Early leaderboard data from ForecastBench [62] confirm a pecking order: *superforecasters* > *regular forecasters* \approx *frontier LLMs* > *older LLMs*.

The most promising gains arise when information flows both ways. On the one hand, exposing LLMs to crowd medians nudges their predictions closer to the truth [39,62]. On the other hand, individual human forecasters equipped with conversational LLM assistants improve substantially [92], even when the assistant is mildly biased, suggesting that the interactive process itself provides augmentation.

Taken together, the evidence reviewed here paints a converging picture. Well-aggregated human crowds still set the accuracy benchmark, yet their diversity and coordination costs curb scalability. Successive generations of LLM, especially when combined into ensembles or retrieval pipelines, have rapidly narrowed the gap, with leading LLMs now matching or exceeding general public performance while still trailing superforecasters. The most promising gains now appear in hybrid settings, where information flows both ways. What remains uncertain is whether increasing LLM accuracy is accompanied by a higher correlation of judgements with human forecasters, as predicted by the ACE. Resolving this question matters because judgement overlap determines whether humans remain complementary or become redundant in future forecasting workflows [41]. In the pages that follow we

map these accuracy–correlation dynamics, providing initial empirical evidence of ACE in modern LLM forecasting and laying the groundwork for re-thinking the division of labour in hybrid prediction systems.

3. The accuracy–correlation effect in language model forecasting

The ACE, formalized by Hong *et al.* [41], describes a fundamental relationship governing hybrid forecasting systems, whereby as algorithmic systems improve in predictive accuracy, they simultaneously become more correlated with human predictions. They attribute this phenomenon to the convergence of two distinct information sources. Algorithms traditionally process ‘big data’ (extensive, granular datasets across numerous dimensions), while humans rely on ‘thick data’ (rich qualitative insights from limited but deeply processed experiential information). As algorithms access increasingly comprehensive datasets, they begin capturing contextual nuances once exclusive to human judgement. This convergence reduces the diversity that makes human–AI combinations valuable, with significant implications for future hybrid forecasting relying on architectures like LLM.

The mathematical formalization of ACE emerges from Hong *et al.*'s application of the bias-variance decomposition theorem [93]. With their analysis they showed that the expected squared error of an optimally weighted hybrid prediction comprising human (h) and algorithmic (c) forecasts of an outcome V can be expressed as

$$\mathbb{E}[(w_c c + w_h h - V)^2] = \frac{\theta \text{Var}(c) \text{Var}(c) - \text{Cov}(h, c)^2}{(1 + \theta) \text{Var}(c) - 2 \text{Cov}(h, c)}, \quad (3.1)$$

where θ represents the accuracy ratio of the algorithm relative to human predictors, $\text{Var}(c)$ denotes the variance of algorithmic predictions and $\text{Cov}(h, c)$ signifies the covariance between human and algorithmic predictions. The optimal weights assigned to each predictor are derived as

$$w_c = \frac{\theta \text{Var}(c) - \text{Cov}(h, c)}{(1 + \theta) \text{Var}(c) - 2 \text{Cov}(h, c)}, \quad w_h = \frac{\text{Var}(c) - \text{Cov}(h, c)}{(1 + \theta) \text{Var}(c) - 2 \text{Cov}(h, c)}. \quad (3.2)$$

This formulation reveals a critical insight: the optimal weight assigned to human forecasts (w_h) diminishes as both algorithmic accuracy (θ) and human–algorithm correlation ($\text{Cov}(h, c)$) increase. More importantly, the two factors interact multiplicatively, potentially accelerating the declining utility of human input in hybrid prediction systems as algorithms continue to advance.

Another critical nuance in Hong *et al.*'s framework is their distinction between typical and atypical forecasting scenarios, which has profound implications for human value in hybrid systems. Typical cases represent situations where context differs only marginally from historical data available to algorithms, like routine economic forecasts or weather predictions. In contrast, atypical cases involve qualitative changes or novel situations where past data may not be relevant, including natural disasters, elections, financial meltdowns or unprecedented innovations. For such situations, Hong *et al.* argue that human forecasters retain comparative advantages through their unique cognitive capabilities, such as reasoning from analogy, imagining alternative futures, understanding causal mechanisms in novel contexts and adapting to qualitative shifts in the environment. This distinction suggests that even as algorithms progressively dominate routine prediction tasks, human forecasters will continue adding distinctive value in scenarios characterized by novelty, complexity or discontinuity, creating an enduring complementarity between human and algorithmic prediction.

ACE has particular salience when applied to LLMs in forecasting contexts. Unlike traditional algorithms with narrowly defined feature spaces, LLMs are trained on massive collections of human-generated text spanning countless domains and perspectives, potentially accelerating the convergence between ‘thick’ human data and ‘big’ algorithmic data that Hong *et al.* identify as driving ACE. If ACE manifests in LLM forecasting, it suggests a progressive decrease in optimal weight assigned to human input in hybrid architectures as AI advances, though humans retain substantial comparative advantages in atypical scenarios where historical patterns provide limited guidance. The theoretical predictions of Hong *et al.* and recent empirical studies on LLM forecasting capabilities provide the foundation for our investigation. Specifically, we examine whether these effects manifest in contemporary LLM-based systems by analysing the relationship between LLM accuracy and AI correlation with human forecasts across multiple model architectures and prompting conditions.

(a) Methodological approach

To investigate ACE in LLM forecasting, we analysed publicly available data from the ForecastBench dataset [63], focusing on 580 resolved forecasting questions from the 21 July 2024 release. A crucial feature of this benchmark is its design to eliminate the risk of data leakage. By construction, all forecasts are elicited for questions about future events that are unresolved at the time of submission, ensuring that model training cut-offs cannot overlap with resolution data.

Following ForecastBench categorization, questions were classified by source: market questions ($n = 54$) from prediction markets and forecasting platforms (*Metaculus*, *Manifold*, *Polymarket*, *RFI*), and data questions ($n = 526$) generated from structured datasets tracking real-world indicators using fixed templates. While this source-based classification is not equivalent to Hong *et al.*'s theoretical distinction between ‘typical’ and ‘atypical’ forecasting scenarios, we use it as a coarse empirical proxy. Market and data questions differ systematically in their sources and construction methods. Data questions are constructed by applying templates to time-series data (e.g. ‘Will indicator X have increased by date Y?’), making them more amenable to pattern recognition from historical trends. Market questions are typically selected by forecasting platforms for their intrinsic interest and difficulty, often involving unique geopolitical events, policy decisions or other contexts where simple extrapolation may be insufficient. We validated that this classification correlates moderately with LLM-rated question typicality (electronic supplementary materials

§ii), though we acknowledge substantial within-category heterogeneity and the marked imbalance in sample sizes. This proxy should be interpreted cautiously and primarily serves to test whether the accuracy–correlation relationship generalizes uniformly or shows systematic variation across forecasting contexts.

Our analysis focused exclusively on resolved questions to ensure evaluation against definitive ground truths. We examined forecasts collected by the ForecastBench research team from 16 LLMs spanning five major AI laboratories: OpenAI (*GPT-3.5-Turbo-0125*, *GPT-4*, *GPT-4-Turbo-2024-04-09*, *GPT-4o*), Anthropic (*Claude-2.1*, *Claude-3-Haiku-20240307*, *Claude-3-Opus-20240229*, *Claude-3-5-Sonnet-20240620*), Google (*Gemini-1.5-Flash*, *Gemini-1.5-Pro*), Mistral AI (*Mistral-Large-Latest*, *Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-V0.1*, *Mixtral-8x22B-Instruct-V0.1*) and Meta (*Llama-2-70b-Chat-Hf*, *Llama-3-8b-Chat-Hf*, *Llama-3-70b-Chat-Hf*). The selection of the models was based on the availability of forecasts across a variety of prompting configurations. These configurations ranged from baseline methods—zero-shot (baseline LLM response without specialized reasoning instructions), scratchpad (structured reasoning prompts) and scratchpad with news retrieval (reasoning prompts enhanced with relevant news articles)—to three distinct prompts developed by superforecasters (P1: Superforecaster Prompt 1; P2: Superforecaster Prompt 2; P3: Superforecaster Prompt 3). The selection was inclusive of models with only a subset of these configurations available. For instance, the Llama and older GPT models were included with only zero-shot and scratchpad forecasts. However, we excluded models with insufficient generational history for our analysis, such as Qwen, for which data from only one model was available. This process yielded 76 distinct forecasting sets, with each set comprising one model’s forecasts under a single prompting condition across the 580 questions. We restricted our analysis to configurations where LLMs generated forecasts without access to crowd predictions, ensuring we assessed the intrinsic forecasting capabilities of models rather than their ability to leverage existing human judgements. This decision allowed us to isolate the relationship between model accuracy and human–AI correlation that constitutes the core of the ACE hypothesis.

Human forecasting data from the ForecastBench dataset provided essential comparison benchmarks from two distinct groups. The *superforecasters crowd* consisted of expert forecasters with established track records of exceptional predictive accuracy, achieving a mean Brier score of 0.118 (median 0.040, s.d. 0.136) on the 580 questions. The *general public crowd* comprised non-expert forecasters recruited through Prolific, representing typical human judgement capabilities, with a mean Brier score of 0.154 (median 0.117, s.d. 0.154). Both human groups exhibited better performance on market questions compared to data questions (superforecasters: 0.082 versus 0.121; general public: 0.122 versus 0.157), though statistical tests revealed these differences were not significant (superforecasters: $t(58.3) = -1.51$, $p = 0.136$; general public: $t(60.1) = -1.32$, $p = 0.191$). The observed effect sizes (Cohen’s $D = -0.291$ and -0.228 , respectively) suggest small-to-medium practical differences that may reflect varying cognitive processes underlying forecasting across question sources.

We employed two primary metrics to assess the ACE. Forecasting accuracy was measured as $(1 - \text{Brier score})$, where the Brier score represents the mean squared error between probabilistic forecasts and binary outcomes [94]. Brier scores were calculated for each individual question first and then averaged across questions for each model. The linear transformation $(1 - \text{Brier score})$ maintained the rank order of performance while providing an intuitive scale where higher values indicated greater accuracy. As for human–AI correlation, we calculated the Pearson correlation coefficient between each LLM’s forecast set and the aggregated human forecasts (analysed separately for superforecasters and general public predictions) across two groupings: market questions only ($n = 54$) and data questions only ($n = 526$).

To assess the ACE while accounting for the hierarchical structure of our data, we employed linear mixed-effects models with human–AI correlation as the dependent variable and standardized LLM accuracy (z -scored $1 - \text{Brier score}$) as the primary predictor. Our data comprised 304 observations from 76 model configurations across two question sources (data versus market) and two forecaster groups (superforecasters versus general public). The base model included fixed effects for accuracy, question source, forecaster group and prompting configuration, with random intercepts for individual LLMs. Model selection followed likelihood ratio testing, with fit evaluated using marginal and conditional R^2 values. An extended model included two-way interactions between accuracy, question source and forecaster group to examine moderation of the accuracy–correlation relationship. Model diagnostics included assessment of residual patterns, heteroscedasticity, normality and influential observations (Cook’s distance, leverage). Robustness was verified through leave-one-model-out analysis and parametric/nonparametric bootstrap validation (1000 iterations). All reported effects represent associations, not causal inferences.

To determine whether the observed accuracy–correlation relationship could be explained solely by humans and LLMs both tracking the same underlying truth, we constructed an independent-error null model. For each LLM configuration, we simulated 1000 binary events with true probabilities drawn from $\text{Uniform}[0, 1]$, generated human forecasts by adding Gaussian noise, and calibrated LLM forecast noise to match empirical accuracy levels. We estimated ACE slopes under this null using both simple linear regression (300 iterations) and mixed-effects models (100 iterations) and compared resulting null distributions to empirical slopes. Additionally, to examine shared error structure directly, we computed question-level errors ($\epsilon_H = H - S$ and $\epsilon_M = M - S$, where S is the resolved outcome and H and M denote the human and LLM forecasts, respectively), and calculated error correlations, error covariances and forecast correlations within each (model, human group, question source) cell. Each quantity was regressed on standardized accuracy separately for data and market questions. Finally, to decompose human–LLM correlation into components associated with overall accuracy versus shared residual errors, we fit a minimal additive mixed-effects model with only standardized accuracy and standardized error correlation as fixed effects (plus a random intercept for LLM). This minimal specification avoided multicollinearity issues that would arise from including additional covariates and preserved interpretability of the additive decomposition.

Figure 1. Average LLM performance across prompting configurations and forecasting questions. Left panel shows superforecaster correlations. Right panel shows general public correlations. Colours indicate AI lab affiliation. Top-performing models achieve both high accuracy and strong human correlation.

(b) Results

(i) Empirical evidence for the accuracy–correlation effect

Our analysis of 304 observations across 16 LLMs provided strong empirical evidence for the ACE. Figure 1 illustrates this pattern at the model level: averaging across prompting configurations, more accurate models consistently exhibit stronger correlations with both superforecaster and general public forecasts. This pattern holds consistently across AI labs, though with variation in slope and range (electronic supplementary material, figure S1). Mixed-effects modelling revealed that LLM forecasting accuracy is significantly and positively associated with human–AI prediction correlation, with this relationship varying systematically across question sources and forecaster groups.

Model selection procedures confirmed that including accuracy as a predictor substantially improved model fit. Likelihood ratio testing demonstrated that the full model incorporating accuracy, question source, forecaster group and prompt configuration significantly outperformed a baseline model without accuracy ($\chi^2 = 122.89$, d.f. = 1, $p < 0.001$; electronic supplementary material, table S1). The variance explained by the model was substantial, with marginal $R^2 \approx 0.38$ and conditional $R^2 \approx 0.63$, indicating that fixed effects alone explained 38% of variance while the complete model (including random effects) explained 63%.

Our final mixed-effects model revealed a robust positive relationship between LLM accuracy and human–AI correlation (electronic supplementary materials, tables S2 and S3). Each unit increase in standardized accuracy corresponded to a 0.080 point increase in correlation coefficients (95% CI: [0.068, 0.093], $t(295) \approx 12.30$, $p < 0.001$). When both variables were standardized, the effect size was medium to large ($\beta \approx 0.516$, 95% CI: [0.434, 0.598], $p < 0.001$), indicating that a 1 s.d. increase in accuracy corresponds to approximately 0.5 s.d. increase in human–AI correlation.

Question source significantly moderated correlation strength, with market questions showing systematically lower correlations than data questions ($\beta \approx -0.043$, s.e. ≈ 0.010 , $t(279) \approx -4.22$, $p < 0.001$). Superforecasters exhibited lower correlations with AI predictions compared to the general public ($\beta \approx -0.056$, s.e. ≈ 0.010 , $t(278) \approx -5.56$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that expert forecasters employ judgement strategies that diverge more from LLM patterns even as model accuracy improves. Prompting configuration effects were modest, with only the ‘Reasoning+News’ configuration showing statistical significance ($\beta \approx 0.040$, s.e. ≈ 0.018 , $t(285) \approx 2.22$, $p \approx 0.027$). The overall prompting effect was marginal ($F(5, 290) \approx 1.79$, $p \approx 0.115$), indicating that the fundamental accuracy–correlation relationship largely transcends specific prompting strategies. Random effects analysis revealed meaningful variation between individual models ($\sigma^2 \approx 0.005$) relative to residual variance ($\sigma^2 \approx 0.008$), indicating that models differ systematically beyond what is captured by fixed effects alone.

An extended model testing two-way interactions revealed that the accuracy–correlation relationship differs significantly by question source (electronic supplementary material, table S4). The Accuracy \times Question Source interaction was significant ($\beta \approx -0.059$, s.e. ≈ 0.015 , $t(287) \approx -4.05$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the accuracy–correlation relationship is attenuated for market questions relative to data questions. This differential aligns with theoretical predictions that ACE manifests more strongly in typical forecasting scenarios, if we consider market questions being atypical. The Question Source \times Forecaster Group interaction was also significant ($\beta \approx -0.079$, s.e. ≈ 0.019 , $t(275) \approx -4.12$, $p < 0.001$), showing that the difference between superforecasters and the general public is more pronounced for market questions. The Accuracy \times Forecaster Group interaction was non-significant ($\beta \approx 0.011$, s.e. ≈ 0.010 , $t(275) \approx 1.17$, $p \approx 0.242$), suggesting the accuracy–correlation relationship operates similarly for both forecaster crowds.

Figure 2. LLM accuracy predicts human–AI correlation. Human–LLM correlation is plotted against standardized LLM accuracy (1 – mean Brier score) for data questions (left panel) and market questions (right panel). Points show individual (model, human group) cells for superforecasters (blue) and the general public (red). Coloured lines and shaded bands give linear fits and 95% confidence intervals from empirical data. The black line shows the corresponding slope under the independent-errors null model. In both panels, the empirical ACE slopes for data and market questions clearly exceed the null benchmark.

Bootstrap analysis confirmed the robustness of our estimates through both parametric and nonparametric resampling approaches (1000 iterations each; electronic supplementary material, table S5). Parametric bootstrap yielded tight confidence intervals for the accuracy coefficient (95% CI: [0.068, 0.093]), while nonparametric bootstrap produced wider intervals (95% CI percentile: [0.056, 0.173]; BCa: [0.053, 0.168]), reflecting the influence of few extreme observations in the dataset, particularly two highly influential cases involving low-accuracy models. Despite this difference in interval width, both approaches confirm that the accuracy–correlation relationship remains statistically significant and practically meaningful, with the lower bounds of all intervals excluding zero. The convergence between parametric and nonparametric methods under conservative assumptions accounting for outlier influence supports the fundamental reliability of the ACE across the full range of model performance.

(ii) Accuracy versus correlated errors

To investigate whether the ACE could be explained purely by the fact that humans and LLMs are both correlated with the underlying truth, we constructed an explicit independent-errors null model. For each LLM configuration, we simulated $N = 1000$ binary events with true probabilities drawn from a Uniform[0, 1] distribution. Human forecasts were generated by adding Gaussian noise to the true probabilities and truncating to [0, 1]. For each LLM, we calibrated the noise standard deviation of the simulated model forecasts to match its empirical accuracy via a simple mapping from accuracy to a Brier score equivalent variance, so that the simulated models span the same accuracy range as the real LLMs. For each simulated dataset, we then computed accuracy and human–LLM correlation and estimated the ACE both with a simple linear regression and with a mixed-effects model that mirrors our empirical specification (including the same fixed effects and a random intercept for Model). Under this independent-errors null, the expected ACE is indeed non-zero, as anticipated. In the simple linear model simulations (300 iterations), the mean null slope for all questions is approximately 0.034 (95% simulation interval: 0.030–0.039). In the mixed-effects simulations (100 iterations), the mean null slope is approximately 0.029 (95% interval: 0.025–0.034). In contrast, the empirical ACE in our data is 0.081 per standard deviation of accuracy (likelihood ratio test versus a model without the accuracy term: $\chi^2(1) \approx 122.89$, $p < 0.001$). In both simulation frameworks, none of the simulated slopes reach the empirical value. Thus, the effect we observe is considerably stronger than what would be expected from the trivial fact that humans and LLMs are both correlated with the truth under an independent-errors model. When we split questions by type, the same qualitative pattern holds. For data questions, the empirical ACE is $\beta_{\text{data}} \approx 0.071$. The corresponding independent-errors LM null yields a mean slope of about 0.042 (95% interval: 0.036–0.048), and the mixed-effects null gives a mean slope of about 0.037 (95% interval: 0.028–0.045). For market questions, the empirical ACE is $\beta_{\text{market}} \approx 0.057$, whereas the LM null has a mean slope of about 0.025 (95% interval: 0.019–0.030) and the mixed-effects null a mean slope of about 0.021 (95% interval: 0.016–0.027). In both subsets (figure 2), the empirical slopes lie well above the corresponding null distributions, indicating that the ACE is not only present overall, but remains stronger than expected from shared grounding in the truth for both data and market questions considered separately.

Mathematically, the independent-errors null can be written as a signal plus noise model in which human and LLM forecasts take the form

$$H = S + \varepsilon_H, \quad M = S + \varepsilon_M,$$

where S is the latent ‘true’ probability and $\varepsilon_H, \varepsilon_M$ are zero-mean residuals. Let

$$\sigma_S^2 = \text{Var}(S), \quad \sigma_{\varepsilon_H}^2 = \text{Var}(\varepsilon_H), \quad \sigma_{\varepsilon_M}^2 = \text{Var}(\varepsilon_M).$$

By construction, the null imposes

$$\text{Cov}(\varepsilon_H, \varepsilon_M) = 0 \iff \text{Corr}(\varepsilon_H, \varepsilon_M) = 0,$$

for all models: humans and LLMs share the same signal S , but their remaining errors are uncorrelated. Since

$$\text{Var}(H) = \sigma_S^2 + \sigma_{\varepsilon_H}^2, \quad \text{Var}(M) = \sigma_S^2 + \sigma_{\varepsilon_M}^2$$

and

$$\text{Cov}(H, M) = \text{Cov}(S + \varepsilon_H, S + \varepsilon_M) = \text{Var}(S) + \text{Cov}(S, \varepsilon_M) + \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_H, S) + \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_H, \varepsilon_M),$$

the assumptions $\text{Cov}(S, \varepsilon_H) = \text{Cov}(S, \varepsilon_M) = 0$ and $\text{Cov}(\varepsilon_H, \varepsilon_M) = 0$ imply

$$\text{Cov}(H, M) = \sigma_S^2.$$

Hence, the correlation between human and model forecasts under the null is

$$\text{Corr}(H, M) = \frac{\text{Cov}(H, M)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(H)}\sqrt{\text{Var}(M)}} = \frac{\sigma_S^2}{\sqrt{(\sigma_S^2 + \sigma_{\varepsilon_H}^2)(\sigma_S^2 + \sigma_{\varepsilon_M}^2)}}. \quad (3.3)$$

Once we calibrate $\sigma_{\varepsilon_M}^2$ to match each model’s empirical accuracy, the independent-errors null fully determines the ‘trivial’ ACE slope that arises purely because both humans and LLMs track the same underlying signal. The fact that the empirical ACE systematically exceeds this benchmark (both overall and within data and market questions) means that, at a given accuracy level, human and LLM forecasts co-move more than can be explained by shared truth alone. This excess co-movement must come from some positive association in the residuals (i.e. a component of their remaining errors, heuristics or inductive biases that is shared), even though the aggregate slopes do not allow us to uniquely identify the size or detailed structure of that shared component.

To investigate this residual structure more directly, we turn to the raw ForecastBench data and compute human and model errors at the question level. For each LLM configuration, human group (superforecasters versus general public) and question source (data versus market), we define the human and model errors on each question as

$$e_H = H - S, \quad e_M = M - S,$$

where S is the resolved outcome, H is the superforecasters or public aggregate forecast and M is the LLM forecast. Within each (model, human group, question source) cell we then estimate three quantities:

- (i) the correlation of errors $\text{Corr}(e_H, e_M)$;
- (ii) the covariance of errors $\text{Cov}(e_H, e_M)$;
- (iii) the correlation of forecasts $\text{Corr}(H, M)$.

Model accuracy in that cell is defined as

$$\text{Accuracy} = 1 - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (f_i - s_i)^2,$$

that is 1 – mean Brier score, and we standardize this accuracy measure across all cells. We then regress each quantity on standardized accuracy, separately for data versus market questions and for superforecasters versus the general public (figure 3). Two robust patterns emerge. First, across all four panels, $\text{Corr}(e_H, e_M)$ is consistently positive and increases with model accuracy (figure 3B). Error correlations are systematically lower for low-accuracy models and increase with accuracy. High-accuracy models, in contrast, display substantially stronger error correlations, especially on data questions: when they are wrong, they tend to be wrong in more human-like ways. Second, the covariance plots clarify why shared-error covariance need not increase monotonically with accuracy (figure 3C). We find that $\text{Cov}(e_H, e_M)$ is strictly positive in all panels, confirming the presence of shared residual structure, but its trend with accuracy is flat (for market questions) or even slightly negative (for data questions). This is expected once we recall the standard relationship between covariance, correlation and standard deviations:

$$\text{Cov}(e_H, e_M) = \text{Corr}(e_H, e_M) \sigma_{e_H} \sigma_{e_M}, \quad (3.4)$$

where

$$\sigma_{e_H}^2 = \text{Var}(e_H), \quad \sigma_{e_M}^2 = \text{Var}(e_M).$$

As LLMs become more accurate, $\sigma_{e_M}^2 = \text{Var}(e_M)$ shrinks: the models make much smaller errors in absolute terms. The product of standard deviations $\sigma_{e_H} \sigma_{e_M}$ therefore declines quickly (figure 3D), faster than the absolute value of the covariance. The result is a

Figure 3. Shared error structure between human and model forecasts across model accuracy. (A–D) Summary statistics for superforecasters and the general public, separately for data (left) and market (right) questions, as functions of standardized model accuracy (1 – mean Brier score). (A) Correlation of human and model forecasts, $\text{Corr}(H, M)$. (B) Correlation of human and model errors, $\text{Corr}(e_h, e_m)$. (C) Covariance of human and model errors, $\text{Cov}(e_h, e_m)$. (D) Product of human and model error standard deviations, $\sigma_h \sigma_m$. Forecast and error correlations increase with accuracy, whereas the covariance and $\sigma_h \sigma_m$ tend to decline, indicating that shared errors become smaller in magnitude but more aligned as models become more accurate.

regime in which (i) the absolute magnitude of shared error decreases (lower covariance), but (ii) the directional correlation of the remaining errors increases (higher correlation). In other words, more accurate LLMs not only track the truth better, the mistakes they still make become rarer and smaller, but also more similar to the mistakes made by human forecasters.

To quantify how much of human–LLM forecast correlation is driven by overall accuracy versus shared residual errors, we decomposed $\text{Corr}(H, M)$ into components associated with overall accuracy and shared residual error. Using a minimal additive mixed-effects specification with a random intercept for LLM, we found that both factors contributed independently and substantially to correlation. A 1 s.d. increase in accuracy was associated with an increase of approximately 0.076 in $\text{Corr}(H, M)$ ($\hat{\beta}_{\text{acc}} \approx 0.076$, $s.e. \approx 0.006$, $t \approx 12.80$, $p < 0.001$), while a 1 s.d. increase in residual-error correlation was associated with an increase of approximately 0.047 ($\hat{\beta}_{\text{err}} \approx 0.047$, $s.e. \approx 0.005$, $t \approx 9.23$, $p < 0.001$). Importantly, adding residual-error correlation significantly improved model fit beyond accuracy alone ($\chi^2(1) \approx 75.62$, $p < 0.001$). This analysis confirms that ACE reflects both improved tracking of the underlying signal and increasingly human-like residual errors.

4. Discussion

Our study provides empirical evidence for the ACE in language model forecasting. Mixed-effects modelling confirmed a robust positive relationship between LLM forecasting accuracy and human–AI prediction correlation, with this relationship remaining significant even when controlling for question source, prompting configurations and forecaster group while accounting for dependencies between individual models. Critically, extended analysis revealed that ACE manifests differentially across contexts: the accuracy–correlation relationship is significantly attenuated for market-sourced questions compared to data-generated questions,

consistent with theoretical predictions that ACE could operate more strongly in typical forecasting scenarios. Throughout the accuracy range, superforecasters consistently exhibited lower correlations with AI predictions than the general public. This pattern indicates that as LLMs improve, they increasingly align with general population forecasting patterns rather than expert judgement. This ‘crowd convergence’ pattern suggests AI systems may be fundamentally oriented towards identifying and reproducing statistical regularities in collective human judgement rather than emulating the sophisticated reasoning strategies that distinguish expert forecasters. Moreover, as LLM-assisted forecasting becomes increasingly common in practice, this convergence may intensify through a feedback loop where humans rely on AI tools trained on human data, further homogenizing judgement patterns. These findings substantiate Hong *et al.*'s theoretical framework while revealing systematic variation in how ACE manifests across different forecasting contexts and forecaster populations.

Beyond confirming ACE, our findings illuminate its underlying mechanisms and reveal a surprising pattern. Comparison with an independent-errors null model demonstrates that the empirical accuracy–correlation relationship substantially exceeds what would be expected if humans and LLMs merely shared correlation through tracking the same truth. Detailed error structure analysis reveals that while error correlations consistently increase with model accuracy, error covariances remain flat or decline as error variance shrinks. The result is a regime where more accurate models make rarer and smaller errors, but those remaining errors exhibit stronger directional correlation with human mistakes. Decomposition analysis confirms that both accuracy and shared residual errors independently contribute to human–LLM correlation, indicating a hybrid phenomenon rather than accuracy gains alone.

To our knowledge, this represents the first systematic evidence that human–LLM correlation operates not only through improved signal tracking but also through increasingly correlated error patterns at the residual level. This has important practical and theoretical implications. First, accuracy gains do not automatically translate into cognitive diversity; models can simultaneously become more accurate and more homogeneous in their failure modes, consistent with recent concerns about algorithmic monoculture and model collapse [58,59,95]. Second, monitoring accuracy metrics alone may obscure problematic convergence at the error level; high-performing systems can fail identically in ways that aggregate metrics miss. Most fundamentally, our results suggest that errors are not mere noise but exhibit structure that is shared across humans and LLMs. This directional correlation of mistakes points to the existence of features or patterns in the forecasting problem space that systematically mislead different cognitive architectures. Humans and LLMs appear to be learning not just the same answers, but the same failure modes. A pattern consistent with evidence that AI representations converge towards shared statistical structures of reality [96]. Whether this reflects inherent properties of forecasting tasks, human-generated training data encoding cognitive biases into model representations or fundamental constraints on inductive inference remains open. Regardless, the finding challenges assumptions that combining human and AI predictions will necessarily yield diversity benefits, particularly as models approach human-level accuracy.

The practical implications of ACE emerge from how it varies across forecasting contexts. Our finding that the accuracy–correlation relationship weakens substantially for market-sourced questions suggests LLMs may achieve parity with human forecasters at different rates depending on forecasting scenario characteristics. However, we must interpret this cautiously, as our market/data categorization serves as a coarse empirical proxy for the theoretical distinction between typical and atypical scenarios, with substantial within-category heterogeneity and marked sample size imbalance. Nevertheless, the pattern suggests that in settings where historical patterns reliably inform outcomes and data are abundant, algorithmic advantages in pattern recognition may enable rapid convergence with human performance. In contrast, scenarios involving unprecedented events or analogical reasoning may preserve human comparative advantages for longer. The observation that expert–public differences are more pronounced for market questions further suggests that superforecaster capabilities (synthesizing diverse information, detecting regime changes, reasoning under deep uncertainty) retain particular value precisely where algorithmic approaches face inherent limitations. Future work employing more refined taxonomies based on cognitive demands rather than question origins could better delineate where ACE manifests strongly versus where human judgement remains indispensable. Despite ACE's general operation, human superforecasters currently outperform even the best LLM configurations, suggesting the frontier of complementarity continues to evolve rather than disappear.

These observations compel a reassessment of how human and algorithmic forecasts should be combined. Hong *et al.*'s mathematical framework demonstrates that optimal weight assigned to human predictions in hybrid ensembles diminishes as both algorithmic accuracy and human–algorithm correlation increase. Our results show both factors rising simultaneously as LLM capabilities advance. This trajectory has important implications for forecasting system design, as the challenge extends beyond simple accuracy comparisons. Hybrid systems derive value from diversity and complementarity between predictors, benefits that erode as information sources converge [97]. Hong *et al.* theorized this convergence occurs when algorithms processing ‘big data’ increasingly capture nuances traditionally embedded in human-leveraged ‘thick data’. LLMs may accelerate this convergence by training on vast corpora of human-generated text, potentially reproducing not only human knowledge but also human reasoning patterns and biases. This concern resonates with broader discussions about synthetic data and model collapse, where over-reliance on machine-generated content risks narrowing informational diversity and weakening ensemble robustness [95]. However, the persistence of differential patterns across question sources (particularly the attenuated ACE for market questions and stronger expert advantages in these contexts) suggests some enduring complementarity in scenarios where historical patterns provide limited guidance and human adaptability retains distinctive value [41,42,98].

Rather than signalling obsolescence, ACE may indicate an evolution in human contributions to forecasting. As algorithmic capabilities expand, human value may increasingly concentrate in higher-order functions that complement rather than duplicate machine processing [46,47,99]. This represents a transition from simple ensemble architectures (where predictions are merely weighted and averaged) to collaborative systems where humans and AI interact dynamically. In this reconfigured landscape, human forecasters might shift from primary predictors to meta-predictors, taking on roles such as identifying when algorithmic

systems are likely to fail, detecting paradigm shifts that invalidate historical patterns, providing contextual framing for novel situations or flagging counterfactual and ethical considerations that algorithms cannot readily process [100–103]. Such roles leverage distinctly human capabilities, like reasoning from analogy, imagining alternative futures, understanding causal mechanisms in unprecedented contexts, while allowing AI to handle data processing and pattern recognition at scale. In essence, human forecasters may be moving from the factory floor to the control room, becoming quality control experts for an AI-powered prediction factory. This dynamic aligns with the conceptualization of hybrid intelligence as achieving superior results through complementary combination rather than substitution [104], with each component focusing on domains where it maintains comparative advantages. The persistence of superforecaster outperformance, particularly on atypical questions, suggests this complementarity remains substantive rather than transitional.

A productive framing positions LLMs not as replacements, but as cognitive partners [105–108] within evolving CI systems. Such human–AI collaboration can be seen as a novel form of CI, potentially overcoming the limitations of purely human groups [32,109,110]. In forecasting, this partnership would leverage the complementary cognitive strengths of humans and AI. The increasing overlap between human and machine predictions highlights the critical need to identify and cultivate areas where human cognition offers unique advantages. This approach fosters ‘collaborative intelligence’ where human and machine components adapt to maximize mutual strengths and compensate for weaknesses, leading to more robust hybrid systems [99,111,112].

Implementing these principles requires reconsidering how forecasting platforms are architected. Traditionally, crowd-forecasting systems have prioritized human judgement with algorithms in support roles [77,113], but our findings suggest more dynamic configurations. The differential manifestation of ACE across question sources implies that platform design should be context-sensitive rather than uniform. LLM advantages in scalability and consistency become particularly valuable for comprehensive question coverage. Unlike human forecasters affected by fatigue [114] and attention limitations [115,116], AI systems can generate forecasts across numerous questions without performance degradation, a significant benefit when human expertise is scarce or expensive. However, the key design challenge lies not in choosing between human and algorithmic forecasting, but in recognizing that optimal configurations likely vary by forecasting context. The differential patterns we observe suggest that one-size-fits-all approaches may be suboptimal, though determining how platforms should adapt architectures to question characteristics requires further investigation.

Several limitations contextualize our findings and indicate directions for future research. Most critically, our market/data categorization serves as a coarse empirical proxy for Hong *et al.*'s theoretical distinction between typical and atypical forecasting scenarios. This categorization involves within-category heterogeneity, sample size imbalance (54 market versus 526 data questions), and relies on question sources rather than direct assessment of cognitive demands or typicality. While we validated that this classification correlates moderately with LLM-rated typicality, future research employing more refined taxonomies could test ACE predictions more rigorously. Second, Hong *et al.*'s theoretical framework focused on dyadic systems (one human, one algorithm), whereas our investigation examined LLM relationships with human crowd aggregates, potentially altering ACE dynamics. Third, our analysis examined predominantly short-term forecasting questions; ACE might manifest differently over longer horizons requiring more complex causal reasoning. Fourth, we analysed models without direct access to crowd predictions; prior work shows models with human forecast access often demonstrate superior performance, suggesting optimal human knowledge integration in hybrid systems requires further investigation. Additionally, our design is observational and cross-sectional; associations between accuracy and human–AI correlation should not be interpreted causally. Similarly, our error structure analysis, while informative about the underlying mechanisms, remains descriptive rather than establishing causal pathways. Finally, our analysis examined correlation at aggregate rather than question level, meaning even highly correlated systems might diverge on specific questions where their comparative advantages differ most. The interaction effects we identified suggest systematic variation by question source and forecaster type but do not reveal which specific question features drive these patterns. Future work could investigate finer-grained predictors of when human–AI complementarity is strongest, enabling more targeted allocation of forecasting resources.

Together, these findings suggest that as LLMs become more accurate, they also become more aligned with human forecasts. This alignment is not uniform across contexts and reflects both improved prediction and shared errors. Rather than replacing human judgement, this suggests a redistribution of roles, with humans retaining value in settings that require contextual and adaptive reasoning. A key open question is whether and how forecasting systems can be designed to continue yielding gains as human and AI forecasts grow increasingly similar.

Ethics. This work did not require ethical approval from a human subject or animal welfare committee.

Data accessibility. All data and code used in this paper are publicly available here: <https://github.com/YonahJ/Accuracy-Correlation-Effect>.

Supplementary material is available online [117].

Declaration of AI use. AI technologies were only used to improve readability and language of the work.

Authors' contributions. Y.J.: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, visualization, writing—original draft; J.S.-M.: conceptualization, formal analysis, project administration, supervision, validation, visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; E.S.-S.: conceptualization, investigation, project administration, supervision, validation, visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing.

All authors gave final approval for publication and agreed to be held accountable for the work performed therein.

Conflict of interest declaration. We declare we have no competing interests.

Funding. No funding has been received for this article.

Acknowledgements. We are grateful to Edmond Seabright for his insightful comments on the independent-errors null model, which substantially strengthened our methodological approach. We thank James Winters and two anonymous reviewers for their constructive feedback, which greatly improved the manuscript. We also acknowledge the support of the School of Collective Intelligence at University Mohammed VI Polytechnic.

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